

ETHNIC HUMOR AS A REFLECTION OF CULTURAL STEREOTYPES

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Abstract

This article examines ethnic humor as a sociocultural phenomenon that reflects and constructs national stereotypes through autostereotypes and heterostereotypes. It analyzes the mechanisms of humor production in interethnic jokes, focusing on the ways in which cultural representations of different national groups are formed, reproduced, and transformed. Particular attention is paid to the structure of interethnic jokes, the role of precedent characters, semantic compression in humor involving proper names, and the emergence of “joke-space stereotypes.” The study also considers the ambivalent nature of ethnic humor, which may function both as a form of harmless cultural commentary and as a vehicle for reinforcing prejudices and discriminatory attitudes.

Keywords

Ethnic humor; stereotypes; autostereotypes; heterostereotypes; interethnic jokes; national character; cultural representation; linguistic humor; precedent phenomena; joke discourse; intercultural communication.

Ethnic humor represents one of the most archaic strata of the comic genre. From the earliest stages of human history, as individuals expanded into new territories and engaged in intercultural contact, they have consistently—often implicitly—positioned themselves as representatives of their own cultural systems in relation to others.

Within any given ethnic community, two principal types of stereotypes can be identified: autostereotypes, which reflect a group's self-perception, and heterostereotypes, which pertain to perceptions of external groups. Autostereotypes typically emphasize those features of national identity that are regarded as most distinctive and socially significant. In contrast, heterostereotypes tend to be evaluative and critical in nature, frequently contributing to the formation and reinforcement of ethnic prejudices. For instance, a trait interpreted as prudence within one's own cultural framework may be reinterpreted as avarice when attributed to another group.

The humorous effect of ethnic anecdotes is grounded in the attribution of specific behavioral patterns to members of particular ethnic groups, regardless of whether such traits correspond to empirical reality. While some examples of ethnic humor function as playful cultural commentary without explicit intent to offend, others display overtly aggressive and derogatory features, thereby aligning with discriminatory or racist discourse. In certain cases, this distinction is embedded in the structural organization of the joke; in others, it depends on the interpretive framework of the audience and the communicative intentions of the speaker.

A particularly salient source of stereotypical representations of national character is the category of interethnic jokes. These are typically structured according to a standardized narrative model in which representatives of different nationalities are placed within an identical situational context and exhibit divergent responses, consistent with culturally

embedded perceptions of national character. Accordingly, interethnic anecdotes rely on heterostereotypes as a mechanism for articulating generalized perceptions of the physical, moral, and cognitive attributes associated with various ethnic groups.

A well-known example illustrates this principle:

Paradise is where cooks are French, mechanics are German, policemen are British, lovers are Italian, and it is all organized by the Swiss. Hell is where cooks are British, policemen are German, lovers are Swiss, mechanics are French, and it is all organized by Italians.

In this anecdote, “paradise” is constructed through positive heterostereotypes, such as French culinary expertise, German technical proficiency, Italian emotional expressiveness, and Swiss organizational efficiency. “Hell,” by contrast, is formed through the inversion of these stereotypes, emphasizing perceived deficiencies. Such representations are rooted in widely circulated cultural narratives that simplify and essentialize national characteristics.

A similar mechanism is observed in the following example:

There have been many definitions of hell, but for the English the best definition is that it is the place where the Germans are the police, the Swedish are the comedians, the Italians are the defense force, Frenchmen dig the roads, the Belgians are the pop singers, the Spanish run the railways, the Turks cook the food, the Irish are the waiters, the Greeks run the government, and the common language is Dutch.

Here, “hell” is constructed through a system of negative heterostereotypes, highlighting perceived shortcomings such as rigidity, lack of humor, disorganization, or incompetence. Importantly, such depictions do not aim to describe reality but rather to expose the reductive nature of stereotypical thinking.

The characters in ethnic anecdotes possess what may be termed a precedent status: they function as mythologized ethnic figures associated with stable images, stereotypes, and standardized patterns of comic behavior within the collective consciousness. Their interpretation is largely accessible only to members of the culture in which the joke circulates. In English-language humor, the most frequent protagonists include representatives of national groups such as the English, Germans, French, Canadians, Mexicans, African Americans, and Poles. The limited range of characters is обусловлено (should be corrected → *is обусловлено* → *is determined*) by the requirement of recognizability and the principle of linguistic economy in the production of comic effect.

For example:

Four students—a British, a French, an American, and a Canadian—were asked to write an essay on elephants...

This anecdote demonstrates how national stereotypes are encoded in culturally specific narrative expectations.

A defining feature of interethnic humor is the deliberate exaggeration of positive traits attributed to one’s own ethnic group alongside the ridicule of characteristics associated with others. These traits are perceived as deviations from an implicit norm and, therefore, as inherently comic. Additionally, humor frequently arises from the depiction of non-native speakers’ violations of grammatical and phonetic norms.

Autostereotypes also play a significant role. These are reflected in anecdotes that ironically highlight the negative features of one’s own group. For instance, Americans often

present themselves as exemplars of democracy, while simultaneously demonstrating a capacity for self-irony by acknowledging its imperfections.

The selection of characters in ethnic anecdotes is not random but is shaped by socio-economic and political conditions, as well as by patterns of intercultural coexistence. These factors may generate tensions and conflicts that are subsequently reflected in humorous discourse. Consequently, a key feature of the modern anecdote is its productivity and variability: as a form of folk discourse, it is continuously reproduced and adapts to current events both within and beyond national boundaries.

Proper names also play a crucial role in anecdote construction. Jokes involving political figures or well-known personalities are characterized by a high degree of semantic compression, requiring at least minimal historical knowledge for their interpretation. Such figures are often attributed behavioral traits perceived as typical of their respective national groups.

Although English-language anecdotes employ universal mechanisms of humor production, they also exhibit specific features. Due to their widespread circulation, many jokes become part of the shared background knowledge of native speakers. As a result, jokes generate their own system of stereotypes—so-called “stereotypes of the joke space.” These may themselves become objects of parody and reinterpretation.

These “anecdote-space” stereotypes primarily concern the appearance, behavior, and personality traits of characters. While they do not fundamentally contradict broader societal stereotypes, they tend to simplify and exaggerate them. The same set of psychological traits may be evaluated differently depending on the perspective of the observer. Thus, qualities such as determination and persistence may be interpreted either positively or negatively depending on the communicative context.

Conclusion

Ethnic humor serves as a complex sociocultural phenomenon that reflects and shapes perceptions of national identity. Through the interplay of autostereotypes and heterostereotypes, jokes both reinforce and challenge existing cultural narratives. While often functioning as a form of entertainment, they also reveal underlying attitudes, tensions, and values within and between cultural communities.

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